

NEURAL MACHINE TRANSLATION AND THE LOSS OF CONTEXT

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Abstract: This paper discusses neural machine translation and context loss. Machine translation is a method that uses computers to automatically translate human languages. Currently, neural machine translation (NMT) has achieved great breakthroughs in translation performance. This paper provides an overview of the structure of NMT and discusses its main problems in terms of context loss.

Keywords: machine translation, neural machine translation, problems, context, loss.

The concept of machine translation (MT) was formally proposed in 1949 by Weaver [1]. He envisioned that modern computers could be used to automatically translate different languages. Since then, machine translation has attracted much attention from scientists and has become one of the most challenging problems in the field of natural language processing and artificial intelligence. Machine translation has recently attracted much attention due to its versatility and speed of translation. Much of the progress in neural machine translation (NMT) is largely due to the invention and development of new neural networks that act as the underlying models for NMT. The main types of neural networks range from recurrent neural network equipped with an attention mechanism, convolutional neural network, and the recently proposed transformer. Neural architecture search [1-3] has also attracted much attention recently due to the fact that it can automatically find neural architectures and give better performance than hand-crafted networks for most tasks. Neural architecture search has had great success in computer vision tasks such as image classification, object detection [1-3]. The author of propose to consider the process of searching for an architecture based on its optimization, namely on one of the most representative methods - gradient-based. It was confirmed that neural architecture optimization is more effective for image classification, but not for neural machine translation. Direct application of optimization to neural MT is not the best choice due to the following reasons:

1. NMT training is sensitive to the choice of hyperparameters. According to preliminary studies, changing even seemingly insignificant indicators can lead to a significant change in the NMT results;

2. Architecture optimization allows finding one level or cell and adds them several times, which leads to a limitation of the architecture space;

3. NMT is usually much larger than an image classification model, which makes it impossible to trace the details of the implementation of standard architecture optimization.

In order for the architecture optimization to have a positive impact on NMT consistent with the above problems, it should be improved according to the following aspects:

1. Design two search spaces: the network operation space, which consists of commonly used architectural components for NMT, such as attention modules, repeating units, etc.

2. Find all layers so that each layer has a customized architecture. This design provides greater flexibility for NMT architectures.

3. Considering that the NMT model usually consists of many parameters, use two methods to solve this problem: shared storage and successive halving [8], which gradually reduces the size of architectural views during the search process, discarding bad ones. From a methodology perspective, MT approaches are mainly divided into two categories: method-rule and method-data. In the rule-based method, bilingual linguists are responsible for designing specific rules to analyze the source language, transform it into the target language, and generate the target language. Since it is subjective and labor-intensive, this method lost its appeal in the early 21st century.

However, the data-driven approach trains computers to translate from many pairs of parallel human-translated sentences. This approach has three main periods. In the mid-1980s, example-based MT was proposed, which translates a sentence by extracting similar examples in pairs of human-translated sentences. Since the early 1990s, statistical machine translation (SMT) has been developed, in which word- or phrase-level translation rules can be automatically learned from parallel corpora using probabilistic models. Since 2014, neural machine translation (NMT) based on deep neural networks has been actively developed [1]. In 2016, various experiments with language pairs showed that NMT has made great progress and received significant improvements compared to previous versions [3]. Neural machine translation is an end-to-end model following an encoder-decoder structure, which typically involves two neural networks [2]. As shown in Figure 1, the encoder network first maps each input token of a source language sentence to a low-dimensional real-valued vector, and then encodes the sequence of vectors into distributed

semantic representations, from which the decoder network generates a token of a target language sentence from left to right.

NMT is formally defined as a sequence-to-sequence prediction problem, which highlights several key issues. First, the input is a sentence instead of paragraphs and documents. Second, the output sequence is formed with left-to-right autoregression. Third, the NMT model is optimized based on the bilingual training data, which should include large-scale parallel sentences to learn good network parameters. Fourth, the processing objects of NMT are pure texts instead of speech and video. Accordingly, we highlight four main issues as follows:

1. In the formulation of NMT, a sentence is the main input for modeling. However, some words in a sentence are ambiguous, and the meaning can only be resolved in the context of surrounding sentences or paragraphs. And when translating a document, we must ensure that the same terms in different sentences lead to the same translation, while performing the translation sentence by sentence independently cannot achieve this goal. It is a big challenge how to fully utilize the contexts beyond sentences in neural machine translation.

2. Non-autoregressive decoding and bidirectional inference. Left-to-right token decoding follows an autoregressive style, which is consistent with human reading and writing. However, it has several drawbacks. On the one hand, the decoding efficiency is very limited because the i -th token of a translation can only be predicted after all $i - 1$ previous predictions have been generated. On the other hand, the prediction of the i -th token can only access the previous history predictions, while it cannot use future context information in an autoregressive manner, resulting in low translation quality.
3. Resource-limited translation. There are thousands of human languages in the world, and abundant bitexts are available only in a few language pairs. Even in a resource-rich language pair, parallel data is unbalanced because most bitexts mainly exist in a few domains. That is, the lack of a parallel learning corpus is very common in most languages and domains. It is well known that neural network parameters can be well optimized for frequently repeated events, and the standard NMT model will be poorly learned on low-resource language pairs. As a result, the question arises how to fully utilize parallel data in other languages (composite translation and multilingual translation) and how to fully utilize non-parallel data.

4. Multimodal neural machine translation. Intuitively, human language is not only texts, and understanding the meaning of language may require the help

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of other modal connections such as speech, images, and videos. In many cases, we are required to translate speech or video. For example, simultaneous speech translation is becoming increasingly popular in various conferences and international live events. Therefore, how to implement multimodal translation in the codec architecture is a big challenge for NMT. How to fully utilize various methods in multimodal translation and how to balance the quality and latency in simultaneous speech translation are two specific challenges. Current NMT systems have a number of shortcomings, which lead to some serious translation errors, which we often see when using complex expressions of the native language. However, the rapid development of NMT technology is actively trying to solve the above problems.

